

Machine learning discoveries of MYC-HOXB8-X gene combinations in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells [†]

Shriprakash Sinha ^{Ⓜ,*}

The three families of (c,L,N)-MYC are known to encode proteins that play significant role as transcription factors in cancer and target various kinds of genes, thus contributing to regrowth and proliferation. Homeobox protein Hox-B8 (HOXB8), is a protein that is implicated in development and known to be highly expressed in colorectal cancer. Treatment of colorectal cancer cells with Porcupine-Wnt inhibitor ETC-1922159 showed down regulation of HOXB8 and MYC, independently. Recently it has been confirmed experimentally that there exists a synergy between MYC-HOXB8. Often, in biology, we are faced with the problem of exploring relevant unknown biological hypotheses in the form of myriads of combination of factors that might be affecting the pathway under certain conditions. Using a machine learning based search engine, I had the opportunity to rank these unknown biological hypotheses for down regulated genes at 3rd order level after the drug was administered. Here, an in silico analysis of the 3rd order combinations of MYC-HOXB8-X (X can be known or unknown factor), from a range of 100 randomly picked down regulated genes after ETC-1922159 treatment, have been presented. Various unknown/unexplored/untested MYC-HOXB8 related 3rd order biological hypotheses emerge, some of which have been confirmed in wet lab, while others need to be tested.

1 Significance

c-MYC and HOXB8 are known to be expressed in colorectal cancer case. Separately, in acute leukaemia, the mechanism by which the combinatorial regulation of c-MYC and HOXB8 happens is not determined. Often, we are faced with the problem of exploring relevant unknown biological hypotheses in the form of myriads of combination of factors that might be involved in the pathway. The current work reveals at in silico level, the 3rd order c-MYC-HOXB8 associated combinations that might be affected by the administration of Porcupine-Wnt inhibitor ETC-1922159 in colorectal cancer. In silico, the current work advances our knowledge of c-MYC-HOXB8-X combinations to facilitate the understanding of Wnt pathway and entail recommended wet lab tests.

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* Corresponding Authors : sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com

Ⓜ Worked as independent researcher

‡ 104 Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai - 490006, India

2 Introduction

2.1 Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

A search engine design has recently been developed in Sinha¹, which showed promise by revealing existing confirmatory published wet lab results. Additionally and of import, adaptation of the engine mined up a range of unexplored/untested/unknown combinations of genetic factors in the Wnt pathway that were affected by ETC-1922159 enantiomer, a PORCN-WNT inhibitor, after the colorectal cancer cells were treated with the inhibitor drug. It was possible to generate the rankings for 3rd order combinations. 100 genes were randomly selected from the list of down regulated genes, by the pipeline and a 3rd order combination was generated from those 100 genes. The total number of gene combination with $C_3^{100} = 161700$. Out of these the MYC-HOXB8 associated 3rd order combinations were selected, which account to a total of 4851 combinations. The goal of this manuscript is to analyse these 3rd order ranked MYC-HOXB8 associations.

2.2 PORCN-WNT inhibitors

The regulation of the Wnt pathway is dependent on the production and secretion of the WNT proteins. Thus, the inhibition of a causal factor like PORCN which contributes to the WNT secretion has been proposed to be a way to interfere with the Wnt cascade, which might result in the growth of tumor. Several groups have been engaged in such studies and known PORCN-WNT inhibitors that have been made available till now are IWP-L6 Chen *et al.*² & Wang *et al.*³, C59 Proffitt *et al.*⁴, LGK974 Liu *et al.*⁵ and ETC-1922159 Duraiswamy *et al.*⁶. In this study, the focus of the attention is on the implications of the ETC-1922159, after the drug has been administered. The drug is a enantiomer with a nanomolar activity and excellent bioavailability as claimed in Duraiswamy *et al.*⁶.

2.3 MYC

c-MYC (MYC) is a gene that encodes for transcription factor. It belongs to the family of MYC genes which includes B-MYC, N-MYC, L-MYC and S-MYC. Mutations in c-MYC have been found to be involved in various kinds of cancers. MYC contains a helix-loop-helix (HLH) and leucine zipper (LZ) domain that helps it to bind to interact with DNA and form a complex with MAX Nair and Burley⁷, respectively. A good introductory review on c-MYC can be found in Dang⁸ which covers topics on transcription factors and binding sites, transcriptional properties, MYC affected genes and finally role of MYC in cell cycle, apoptosis Hoffman and Liebermann⁹ and metabolism Miller *et al.*¹⁰. A lot of work has been done in MYC at various levels as it is implicated in various types of cancer. Additionally, MYC has been found to have influence on the chromatin structure also Knoepfler *et al.*¹¹. In colon cancer, c-MYC has been found to be highly expressed Sikora *et al.*¹² & Smith *et al.*¹³.

2.4 Homeobox protein B8 or HOXB8

Homeobox protein B8 or HOXB8 belongs to the HOX family and is implicated in development Fujimura *et al.*¹⁴. Homeobox proteins are known to play major role in embryogenesis, however, their transition and role in oncogenesis is not clearly established, as there are cases where there is loss of function, while in others, there is gain of function Abate-Shen¹⁵. The HOX family Acampora *et al.*¹⁶ is known to play multiple roles in various tumor cases and varied affects have been found in colorectal tumor and normal cases Kanai *et al.*¹⁷. HOXB8 and HOXB9 are highly expressed in colorectal cancer cases Vider *et al.*¹⁸ & Shen *et al.*¹⁹.

2.5 MYC-HOXB8 interaction

It has been observed that in presence of expressed HOXB8, there is enhancement in the expression of MYC in acute myeloid leukaemia Salmanidis *et al.*²⁰. However, the mechanism by

which the combinatorial regulation of HOXB8 and MYC happens in leukaemia, is yet to be determined. In human embryonic stem cells, MYC is found to bind with MIZ1 via recruitment of DNMT3A (DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 3A) and HDAC (histone deacetylases) to silence HOXB8 Varlakhanova *et al.*²¹. Reversibly, decrease in levels of MYC have lead to increase in HOXB8 expression. Separately, MYC-HOXB8 interaction in colorectal cancer has yet to be investigated and is a subject of on going research. As observed previously, MYC and HOXB8 have been found to be up regulated in colorectal cancer cases and after the administration of ETC-1922159 in specific subtype of colorectal cancer Madan *et al.*²², both were found to be down regulated. Recently, in 2020, Ying *et al.*²³ showed that oncogenic HOXB8 is driven by MYC-regulated super-enhancer and potentiates colorectal cancer invasiveness via BACH1. This wet lab experiment confirms our search engine's indication of the synergy of combination of MYC-HOXB8 in colorectal cancer. Using the in silico analysis, we generated and prioritized 3rd order combinations of MYC-HOXB8-X in these treated colorectal cancer cells Madan *et al.*²², to reveal unknown combinatorial hypotheses regarding probable synergistic down regulation of factors in the Wnt pathway. These emerging unknown hypotheses facilitate oncologists/biologists to navigate a vast combinatorial forest of search space.

3 Results and Discussion

We present here the 3rd order combinations associated with MYC and represent them as MYC-X-X where X can be known or unknown factor from a list of genes that were affected after the administration of the ETC-1922159 drug. There are a total of 4851 combinations of randomly selected 100 genes from a list of 2500± genes. Out of these 100, MYC was one of them. Here we analyse some of the ranked combinations out of 4851 3rd order interactions for MYC-HOXB8-X. Note that the rankings were generated using only the HSIC density index using the radial basis function kernel. Also, the rankings for a particular gene might change over different combinations and the biologists/oncologists are advised to cross check across the different tables presented. However, where possible, we report confirmatory results by the pipeline that fall in line with the published and known mechanism of a particular gene under consideration. Also, many of the combinations are yet to be tested and we make openings for the deeper analysis and exploration of the combinations as future work. These combinations with their rankings have been recored in table 1.

3.1 MYC-HOXB8-X, X - known/unknown/untested factor

DHX9 is a RNA helicase that belongs to the family of DExD/H-box family and is found to be involved in the transcriptional regulation in cancer Lin *et al.*²⁴ & Mi *et al.*²⁵. DHX9 has been found to be up regulated in colorectal cancer cases and after the treatment

of the ETC-1922159, it was down regulated. The combination of HOXB8-DHX9-MYC acquires lower priority of 4, indicating a possible potential synergistic affect (within the selected 100 genes).

METTL12 (methyltransferase-like protein 12) Malecki *et al.*²⁶ was found to be down regulated and the pipeline assigned a low rank of 19 along with MYC-HOXB8. This is in accordance with the down regulation by ETC-1922159 Madan *et al.*²². However, how METTL12 plays a role in colorectal cancer needs to be investigated and research is ongoing. METTL8 (methyltransferase-like protein 8) was also found to be down regulated after the treatment of ETC-1922159. It has been found that the frameshift mutations have occurred in METTL8 in CRC and might be a cause of tumorigenesis through their inactivation in CRC Yeon *et al.*²⁷. It is not known if this is the case with the samples used in experiments of Madan *et al.*²². However, this does point to the fact that if the frameshift mutations played a role in CRC samples of Madan *et al.*²², then ETC-1922159 treatment would have suppressed frameshift mutated METTL8. The pipeline assigns this down regulation with a low rank of 19.

PABPC1L (as recorded by Madan *et al.*²²) or the cytoplasmic 1-like poly(A)-binding protein Gray *et al.*²⁸, belong to a family of multifunctional proteins PABPs which regulate and stabilise the mRNA translation. They are observed to be helpful in the transportation of the mRNA also from the nucleus and there exists a nucleic version of PABP also Kini *et al.*²⁹. PABPC1 contains four non identical RRM domains that are joined with the main PABC domain and separated by a linker. Though their mechanism of import and export of mRNA has not been understood deeply, a few models/observations have been made. Association with translation complexes or mRNA at cytoplasmic level inhibits the transportation of PABPC1 to the nucleus. Contrary to this, its release leads to binding with Importin- α/β complex that facilitates in nuclear import. There are various mechanisms by which PABPC1L might be exported out of the nucleus. Modes of export involve association with (1) cytoplasmic eEF1 α (2) mRNA as well as TAP that mediates the mRNA export and (3) Paxillin via CRM1 pathway. In gastric cancer cases, PABPC1 has been found to be an oncoprotein Zhu *et al.*³⁰ and observed to exert carcinogenesis. In colon cancer mutations in PABPC1 have been found in minor tumor clones Yu *et al.*³¹. Genomic correlates of immune-cell infiltrates in CRC have found the existence of significantly mutated CRC genes Giannakis *et al.*³². PABPC1L was found to be down regulated after the treatment of ETC-1922159 and a low ranking (of 1167) is associated with MYC-HOXB8. In CRC, PABPC1L might be mutated and work as onco-protein and facilitate the transmission of other oncogenic factors. The administration of the drug down regulated the gene in drug treated CRC cells and the low ranking confirms at in silico level the suppression at cytoplasmic level.

Hydroxyacyl-Coenzyme A dehydrogenase is encoded by gene HADH and mutations in the same have been found to cause

hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia Molven *et al.*³³. Deficiency in HADH can lead to a rare condition where body stops converting fat into energy. The authors are not aware of HADH in colorectal cancer and the pipeline indicated a low rank of 1555 along with MYC-HOXB8. After the administration of the drug, HADH was found to be down regulated in the treated colorectal cancer cells with ETC-1922159.

Reduced HUGL1, a homologue of LGL tumor suppressor, is found to contribute to progression of colorectal cancer Schimanski *et al.*³⁴. LGL has been found to arrest G1 cell cycle via formation of a complex involving LGL-VPRBP-DDB1 Yamashita *et al.*³⁵ & Huang and Chen³⁶. Yamashita *et al.*³⁵ show that depletion of VPRBP leads to rescue of over proliferation of LGL-depleted cells. Mutations in VPRBP might lead to cell proliferation in colorectal cancer cases and ETC-1922159 administration show down regulation of VPRBP. Reversibly, down regulation of wild type VPRBP leads to phase progression. Our pipeline shows a down regulation with a high rank of 2997 for the mutated version, however, across different tables, the majority voting points to higher rank. This high rank indicates the wild type VPRBP to be working reversibly and thus point to inhibition of progression of cell proliferation. Alternatively, higher ranks also mean that these combinations might not be important in one specific condition while it might be in another. Further tests are needed for VPRBP.

FZD7 has been found to be highly expressed in colorectal cancer cells Ueno *et al.*³⁷ & Vincan *et al.*³⁸. After the ETC-1922159 treatment, FZD7 was found to be highly suppressed. However, the combination of FZD7-MYC-HOXB8 showed an extremely high rank of 3571, indicating that either the combination of not much importance or FZD7 increases MYC levels Ueno *et al.*³⁹ which then decreases HOXB8 levels (similar to Varlakhanova *et al.*²¹)(if this model works). Reversibly, suppression of FZD7 by ETC-1922159 might lead to suppression of MYC, however, this should increase the levels of HOXB8 (according to the model in Varlakhanova *et al.*²¹), which is not the case after ETC-1922159 treatment. Thus this combination might not be of interest or there is an intricate mechanism between MYC-HOXB8 that is yet to be explored.

Unknown factors XX133 (rank 143), XX229 (rank 362), XX170 (rank 481), XX210 (rank 923), XX115 (rank 1018), XX216 (rank 1160), XX157 (rank 2094), XX92 (rank 2147) were found to be assigned low ranks by the pipeline and this is in accordance with the down regulation of the same due to ETC-1922159 Madan *et al.*²². Probable insight might be that these unknown factors have similar priority for up regulation in colorectal cancer and vice versa after the drug treatment. Biologists might want to investigate these unknown factors and explore their influence apropos MYC-HOXB8. On the other hand, XX13 (rank 2458), XX63 (rank 2459), XX46 (rank 2774), XX198 (rank 3818) and XX144

(rank 4015) were found to be assigned a low rank along with MYC-HOXB8 by the pipeline. These rankings indicate possible non significance after the drug treatment or, there is a reverse mechanism between the components (MYC-HOXB8-XX) that is not known. These unknown factors require investigation in wet lab.

Zinc finger is motif that helps in the stabilisation of the folds via the zinc ions. There are numerous variants of the zinc finger motifs. ZNF215 was recorded to be down regulated after the colorectal cancer cells were treated with ETC-1922159 and not much has been studied regarding ZNF215 in colorectal cancer. The pipeline assigns a low rank of 17 along with MYC-HOXB8 out of the 4851 3rd order interactions with MYC-HOXB8, using 99 randomly chosen down regulated genes. Similar interpretations for ZNF780B (with low rank of 562) and ZNF614 (with low rank of 635) can be derived as the pipeline assigned low ranks for down regulation. Wet lab study regarding these zinc finger variants needs to be done as they emerge as untested 3rd order combination hypotheses.

EZH2 encodes enhancer of zeste homolog 2 and is involved in transcriptional repression via epigenetic modifications. It has been found to be either mutated or over-expressed in many forms of cancer. Over expression of EZH2 leads to silencing of various tumor suppressor genes and thus implicating it for potential roles in tumorigenesis Simon and Lange⁴⁰. EZH2 is a subunit of the highly conserved Polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) which executes the methylation of the histone H3 at lysine-27 OâäMeara and Simon⁴¹. Thus targeting EZH2 has become a major research domain for cancer therapeutics Kim and Roberts⁴². In colon cancer, it has been shown that depletion of EZH2 has led to blocking of proliferation of the cancer Fussbroich *et al.*⁴³. This indicates the fact that tumor suppressor genes get activated and lead to subsequent blocking of the cancer. Also, EZH2 is recruited by PAF to bind with β -catenin transcriptional complex for further Wnt target gene activation, independent of the EZH2 epigenetic modification activities Jung *et al.*⁴⁴. Consistent with these, ETC-15922159 treatment lead to down regulation of EZH2 in colorectal cancer samples Madan *et al.*²². This would have activated a lot of tumor suppressor genes that led to subsequent suppression of regrowth in treated cancer samples. More importantly, MYC directly upregulates core components of PRC2, EZH2 being one of them, in embryonic stem cells Neri *et al.*⁴⁵. Neri *et al.*⁴⁵ show that silencing of c-MYC and N-MYC Dardenne *et al.*⁴⁶ lead to reduction in the expression of PRC2 and thus EZH2. Furthermore, in colorectal cancer cases, Satoh *et al.*⁴⁷ show that knockdown of MYC led to decrease in EZH2 levels. Similar findings have been observed in Yamaguchi and Hung⁴⁸, Chen *et al.*⁴⁹ & Fluge *et al.*⁵⁰. Our in silico findings show consistent results with respect to this down regulation after assigning a low rank of 54 along with MYC-HOXB8. More specifically, our in silico pipeline is able to approximate the value

of the 3rd order combination of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 by assigning a rank that is consistent with wet lab findings of dual combinatorial behaviour of MYC-EZH2 and MYC-HOXB8. However, since the mechanism of combination of MYC-HOXB8 is not known hitherto, it would be interesting to confirm the behaviour of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 at 3rd order to reveal a portion of the Wnt pathway's modus operandi in colorectal cancer. Further wet lab tests on these in silico findings will confirm the efficacy of the search engine in Sinha⁵¹, Sinha⁵².

Not much is known about OSGEPL1 or the O-sialoglycoprotein endopeptidase-like 1 in colorectal cancer case. The experiments of ETC-1922159 Madan *et al.*²² show a down regulation of OS-GEPL1 and the in silico pipeline assigns this down regulation with a rank of 75. Similarly, LYRM7 was found to be down regulated after the drug treatment and not much is known about the role of LYRM7 in colorectal cancer. The pipeline assigned a ranking of 131 along with MYC-HOXB8 combination.

Chromosome 9 open reading frame 152 (C9orf152) has not been studied much, however, it has been found to be up regulated in intrinsic subtypes of gastric cancer Tan *et al.*⁵³. Experiments using ETC-1922159 showed down regulation of C9orf152. The pipeline shows an indication of down regulation with a low rank of 128. Similar interpretations for other open reading frames like C4orf27 (with rank of 148), C1orf53 (with rank of 247) and C3orf33 (with rank of 1643) can be made regarding their down regulation after ETC-1922159 treatment and the rank assignment by the pipeline.

Mitochondrial 39S ribosomal protein L18, is a ribosomal mitochondrial protein that is encoded by MRPL18, that works within the mitochondria for protein synthesis Koc *et al.*⁵⁴. Sasso *et al.*⁵⁵ show that MRPL18 is differentially expressed in ileum tumors from APC^{min/+} mice crossed with iVP16LXR α and iVP16 transgenic mice. Not much has been studied in colorectal cancer case regarding MRPL18. Experiments in Madan *et al.*²² show MRPL18 is down regulated after ETC-15922159 and the in silico predictions point to this with a low rank 249.

Similar interpretations can be made for ranks of other factors with MYC-HOXB8-X (X is variable factor) axis till 1167 in the table 1.

4 Conclusion

Homeobox proteins are known to play major role in embryogenesis, however, their transition and role in oncogenesis is not clearly established, as there are cases where there is loss of function, while in others, there is gain of function. The three families of (c,L,N)-MYC are known to encode proteins that play significant role as transcription factors in cancer and target various kinds of genes, thus contributing to regrowth and proliferation. In colorectal cancer, MYC and HOXB8 are known to be up regulated, however, the dual combinatorial regulation mechanism of

RANKING USING HSIC - RBF KERNEL W.R.T MYC-HOXB8-X					
3^{rd} odr comb.	rbf rank	3^{rd} odr comb.	rbf rank	3^{rd} odr comb.	rbf rank
HOXB8-DHX9-MYC	4	HOXB8-ZNF215-MYC	17	HOXB8-METTTL8-MYC	19
HOXB8-EZH2-MYC	54	HOXB8-OSGEPL1-MYC	75	HOXB8-C9orf152-MYC	128
HOXB8-LYRM7-MYC	131	HOXB8-XX133-MYC	143	HOXB8-MYC-C4orf27	148
HOXB8-C1orf53-MYC	247	HOXB8-MRPL18-MYC	249	HOXB8-MYC-PAAF1	305
HOXB8-XX229-MYC	362	HOXB8-METTTL12-MYC	408	HOXB8-PHF14-MYC	463
HOXB8-MYC-CENPF	472	HOXB8-XX170-MYC	481	HOXB8-SIRT3-MYC	491
HOXB8-TAF9-MYC	506	HOXB8-KBTBD7-MYC	556	HOXB8-ZNF780B-MYC	562
HOXB8-TESC-MYC	575	HOXB8-TNNC2-MYC	587	BANF1-HOXB8-MYC	599
HOXB8-PARS2-MYC	611	HOXB8-ZNF614-MYC	635	ALG8-HOXB8-MYC	651
HOXB8-SHF-MYC	661	HOXB8-E2F2-MYC	675	HOXB8-RPL18A-MYC	742
HOXB8-LRRC2-MYC	768	HOXB8-SLC43A3-MYC	798	HOXB8-AGMAT-MYC	850
HOXB8-ENOX2-MYC	859	HOXB8-FAM81A-MYC	916	HOXB8-XX210-MYC	923
HOXB8-VMA21-MYC	999	HOXB8-XX115-MYC	1018	HOXB8-PDHA1-MYC	1023
HOXB8-HSD17B8-MYC	1058	HOXB8-XX216-MYC	1160	HOXB8-PABPC1L-MYC	1167
HOXB8-GCAT-MYC	1267	HOXB8-TANGO6-MYC	1278	HOXB8-ZBTB2-MYC	1283
HOXB8-ESF1-MYC	1289	HOXB8-GTPBP3-MYC	1295	HOXB8-ANKS6-MYC	1304
HOXB8-CENPM-MYC	1343	HOXB8-ALDH7A1-MYC	1345	HOXB8-THAP11-MYC	1408
HOXB8-ATOH1-MYC	1425	HOXB8-SLC6A6-MYC	1456	HOXB8-PGAP2-MYC	1490
HOXB8-HADH-MYC	1555	HOXB8-ANKRD32-MYC	1615	HOXB8-DNMT3A-MYC	1625
HOXB8-C3orf33-MYC	1643	HOXB8-ACTL8-MYC	1803	HOXB8-KIAA1586-MYC	1809
HOXB8-CHAF1B-MYC	1833	HOXB8-MYC-NDUFS3	1875	HOXB8-UQCRH-MYC	1909
HOXB8-GDF11-MYC	1922	HOXB8-XX157-MYC	2094	HOXB8-TUFM-MYC	2117
HOXB8-XX92-MYC	2147	HOXB8-GPX1P1-MYC	2157	HOXB8-SNRPA1-MYC	2194
HOXB8-PRPF19-MYC	2221	HOXB8-STMN1-MYC	2274	HOXB8-BIRC5-MYC	2309
HOXB8-ATP6V0E2-MYC	2434	HOXB8-SLC25A26-MYC	2437	HOXB8-XX13-MYC	2458
HOXB8-XX63-MYC	2459	CCDC84-HOXB8-MYC	2630	HOXB8-NDUFAF4-MYC	2679
HOXB8-PAXBP1-MYC	2748	HOXB8-XX46-MYC	2774	HOXB8-PBK-MYC	2904
HOXB8-TFAM-MYC	2922	HOXB8-PRIM1-MYC	2981	HOXB8-ACN9-MYC	2992
HOXB8-MYC-VPRBP	2997	HOXB8-CCDC138-MYC	3090	KIF18A-HOXB8-MYC	3189
HOXB8-SCAMP5-MYC	3208	HOXB8-PTTG1-MYC	3437	HOXB8-FZD7-MYC	3571
HOXB8-ADCY3-MYC	3640	HOXB8-HPRT1-MYC	3807	HOXB8-XX198-MYC	3818
HOXB8-GLA-MYC	3835	HOXB8-XX144-MYC	4015	HOXB8-ATP5I-MYC	4127
HOXB8-MYC-UMPS	4252	HOXB8-CBY1-MYC	4564		

Table 1 3^{rd} order interaction ranking using HSIC for radial basis function kernel. Total number of 3^{rd} order interactions in a set of 100 genes - 161700. 4851 3^{rd} order combinations for associated work. Rankings for MYC-HOXB8-X have been tabulated.

MYC and HOXB8, has only recently been discovered experimentally. More specifically, our in silico pipeline is able to approximate the value of the 3^{rd} order combinations like that of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 by assigning a rank that is consistent with wet lab findings down regulation of dual combinatorial behaviour of MYC-EZH2 and MYC-HOXB8 after the ETC-1922159 treatment. It would be interesting to confirm the functional behaviour of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 at 3^{rd} order to reveal a portion of the Wnt pathway's modus operandi in colorectal cancer. Further wet lab tests on these in silico findings will confirm the efficacy of the search engine.

5 Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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7 Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan *et al.*²².

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